

What is about?

ESTELAR is built on three key pillars:

- ✓ Advanced communication strategies
- ✓ A robust computational framework
- ✓ The transformative digital substation of the future architecture

ESTELAR enhances substation communication systems to ensure seamless, real-time integration between physical and virtual components.

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Pioneering Virtual Substations for a Climate-Neutral Future

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Effective Substation Technologies for Advanced virtualization

Why **ESTELAR**?

As Europe transitions to a carbon-neutral economy, power grids must become more flexible, intelligent, and capable of handling the complexities of renewable energy.

ESTELAR is shaping the future of power grid infrastructure.

Core benefits

①

Environmental impact

Contributes to lower carbon emissions and improved energy efficiency through advanced digital substation solutions.

②

Operational efficiency

Improved power distribution and management.

③

Cost effectiveness

Reduced maintenance and operational costs.

Mission

To transform traditional electrical substations into virtual ones through advanced digitalization, contributing to a more sustainable and efficient energy future.

Sustainable Development

SDG 7

Enabling clean energy integration

SDG 9

Innovating infrastructure digitalization

SDG 13

Reducing carbon footprint